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Second and third cycles activity artefacts
collection
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1	Zuhal Yılmaz Doğan Danny Arati Gizem Ağyüz	author	30.10.2019
2	Zuhal Yılmaz Doğan Danny Arati Gizem Ağyüz	author	16.12.2019

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1. INTRODUCTION

The focus of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) is on giving children and young people a clear voice for their concerns and interests in relation to the digital society. In contrast to traditional observation-based research, which can only tell us what people have been doing, the project's generative research approach allows us to gain deeper insights about their motivations, by giving participants free rein to their creativity in expressing their concerns, their attitudes and expectations through a variety of media and formats. This allows their voices to be heard in a variety of ways and provides much deeper access to the potentials of children and young people that the WYRED project is trying to explore, and to make visible in such a way that it can inform policies. The groups' activities are generating a wide range of artefacts, such as videos, digital stories, publications, music, art, reports, images etc. The artefacts will be collected on the WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, García-Holgado, & Seoane-Pardo, 2019; WYRED Consortium, 2018) which, among other things, will be used as a repository of results and raw data generated by the research. These will be published on the WYRED platform, with artefacts freely accessible for public consumption¹.

The present work package focuses on the second and third phases of the WYRED cycle, where the consortium aims to facilitate a wide range of exploratory activities, called research activities, during which groups of children and young people, internationally or locally, investigate and examine the issues that concern them in the digital arena. They do this through creative projects (e.g. prototyping solutions following an ideation session to tackle pre-defined challenges) or more conventional research projects. As in the previous stage, interaction during the research activities will ideally take place on the platform, though some users may prefer other media. Each group working on an open research activity administers a dedicated space on the platform to record and review work progress.

As previously mentioned, the WYRED project is structured in cycles (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b). During the first cycle, research activities for this work package (Phase 03) have been adjusted based on the results of the evaluation work (Phase 04). As shown in the following infographic, the initial set of activities and project plan yielded some artefacts. The subsequent evaluation work allowed us to adjust the aim. Based on the Activity Toolkit and on didactical material created as a core deliverable

¹ <https://platform.wyredproject.eu>

for this work package, workshops with Young People and Children were run with specific goals in mind, systematically producing artefacts.

Figure 1: 2nd Cycle of the WYRED Project

Table 2: 3rd cycle numbers of WP6

Quantitative Indicators	Target value	2 nd & 3 rd cycle value	Total numbers
Average number of active participants per country per cycle	30	99+109	208
Average number of research activities per country per cycle	5	7+ 17	24
Average number of research activities types per cycle	5	12+19	31
Number of artefacts generated per cycle	80	52+ 134	186

2. DELIVERABLE WP6.4: IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVITIES – CYCLE 2 AND 3

Much of the work of deliverable 6.4. involves creative activities by young people in response to a particular question or issue. Since the different research groups involved in the project were meant to design their own processes, it was correctly anticipated that guidance would be welcomed and, to this end, a toolkit of generative research activities (templates and guidelines) was generated as a specific deliverable. The toolkit was distributed to all participants and made available on the WYRED platform. All partners made good use of the activity toolkit while facilitating research activities.

During the 2nd cycle of the project, the participants focused on designing and implementing research activities in order to explore the issues identified in the 2nd Delphi questionnaire. For these research activities 8 topics selected. These topics were influencers on social media, our digital footprints-protecting ourselves, self-image online, gender stereotypes and equality on internet, your lives on social media vs adults, digital participation, gender-stereotypes: the way out. Participants worked internationally in groups to design and implement their own activities, facilitating partner organizations. For this international level, international discussion groups were formed on the WYRED platform. Furthermore, groups were able to present their ongoing work as public projects in the common area in the WYRED platform, and in the respective community areas created for them by the partner organisations. Participants are able to read projects made public by the project owners, as well as comment on them and cast their vote. This allows Young People and Children to compare and contrast their experiences with projects run by peers across participating countries, covering a variety of topics in English and/or in local languages.

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Figure 2: Public projects on the WYRED platform

Figure 3: Community Area on the WYRED platform

Figure 4: International communities

Figure 5: International conversations

3. RESEARCH TOPICS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Research topics and questions were identified through the Delphi and Social Dialogues, data was collected by stakeholders and participants. As a next step, all partner organisations defined four research topics for which a range of activities were then envisaged by participants, including drama, film, creative digital arts, digitally mediated educational and other informal learning activities and other research projects. This stage generated quantitative data, narratives, artefacts and other outputs subject

to interpretation in the following stage by the research participants themselves, the consortium and third parties. The aims to encourage participants, through reporting on their research activities, to generate “thick descriptions” of the processes involved (Geertz, 1973) were achieved overall. The outputs of the research activities are stored in the WYRED platform repository, exploiting data standards relating to generative research methods. Open Access criteria are applied, including about the exploitation of existing platforms².

Artefacts of different kinds, such as videos, sculptures, publications, music, reports, and images, produced during the participant research phase, will be initially stored in the group spaces, and then in the WYRED knowledge base. The artefacts collections will be delivered according to the two cycles implementation.

All partner organisations implemented different sessions and activities with the groups of children, YP and stakeholders to work on the research processes. At the time of writing, some groups have finalised their research and can provide already some conclusions and/or artefacts, while others are still in the process of completing their project.

All current 2nd Cycle project work is listed on the following pages, independently of the status of completion, together with comments and recommendations from participants, if available. In total, by the end of the 2nd Cycle, 895 participants aged 11 to 30 had contributed to 52 projects.

All current 3rd Cycle project work is listed on the following pages, independently of the status of completion, together with comments and recommendations from participants, if available. In total, 871 participants aged 11 to 30 contributed to 134 projects to date.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/wyred?page=1&size=20>

4. LIST OF PROJECTS CYCLE 2

Table 3: Oxfam Italia Onlus' artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Scienze politiche per la Cooperazione e lo Sviluppo all'Università degli Studi di Roma Tre.	Elisabetta Svolacchia	Vittime di bullismo: la storia di chi in sé ha trovato la luce	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunit%C3%A0-italiana/project/vittime-di-bullismo-la-storia-di-chi-s%C3%A9-ha-trovato-la-luce	There are stories that long enjoy the light of the spotlights, others instead, are destined to remain in the shade. The latter are stories of profound suffering, of endless silences, of those who for fear or shame have chosen to hide. But it is precisely to these people that we should give voice and it is for the same reason that I decided to tell, entering on tiptoe into the hemisphere of his solitude, the experience of one of the many victims of bullying. We can no longer ignore, turn away from the other side. Information and words are perhaps the only two instruments that can awaken consciences and allow the same victims to find the strength to say enough: enough to humiliation, endurance, pain.
		I giovani e il mondo del lavoro	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunit%C3%A0-italiana/project/i-giovani-e-il-mondo-del-lavoro	With her research she decided to deepen the relationship of young people and the world of work, asking myself four questions: is there a gap between the working desires of young people and the actual possibility of realizing them? What are the tools that are used today in job hunting? Is the work undergoing progressive democratization or are socio-economic barriers still influential? Are young people aware of the effects of the crisis on the world of work? If you too have asked her own questions or

						are curious to see the answers she has obtained, you can read her research!
		Giovani, identità e politica: una storia alternativa	Qualitative research through interviews	Research project	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/comunit%C3%A0-italiana/project/giovani-identit%C3%A0-e-politica-una-storia-alternativa	This project was born from the need to understand the relationship between young people and politics, starting from the representation of us young as "big babies", uninterested in politics and lazy, produced and disseminated by the politicians and the media themselves.

Table 4: Doga Schools' artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Doga High School	TG	Journey to children's rights	Project presentation	Project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/%C3%A7ocuk-haklarina-yolculuk	As a signatory to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the question of whether children's rights are sufficiently viable is a problematic issue. The aim of the study is to determine the level of awareness of children's rights in the 5th and 6th grade. For this purpose, the questionnaire, which is a quantitative research method, was preferred and applied to 42 participants. Numerical analysis of the data obtained from the survey applied in the research was revealed, the section of the open-ended questions was divided into categories and themes and the findings were interpreted in terms of the awareness of the children's rights in terms of the awareness of the participants.
Doga High School	EB and DG	Definition of society regarding social state understanding	Project presentation	Survey project, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/toplum-sosyal-devlet-anlayi%C5%9Ffinali%C5%9Fkin-tanimi	The social state is network of institutions that provide services to the citizens. In our country, like the European states, social reforms and studies are carried out. These activities are carried out with central or local governments. In this context, social policies were prepared and implemented. The aim of this study is to learn from the participants whether they can define the social state.

Doga High School	EK	Leave the tablet engage with knitting	Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/leave-tablet-engage-knitting	This project aimed to create generating individuals by excluding our children from technological appliances for some time and keeping the values, traditions alive.
Doga High School	TU	Mobile application to detect battery powered/electrical wheelchairs charging stations	Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/mobile-application-detect-battery-poweredelectrical-wheel-chairs	This developed mobile application programme is prepared for physically handicapped people to reach the closest wheelchair charging station easily and fleetly from the place they are in order to make physically handicapped people's life easier.
Doga High School	YDU	Charging mobile devices with electricity generated from movement of the stress wheel, an alternative energy source for mobile people	Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/mobile-insanlar-i%C3%A7in-alternatif-enerji-kayna%C4%9Fi-stres-%C3%A7arki	If people are able to provide electricity from alternative sources for at least their basic needs in daily life, the need to invest in conventional production sources will be reduced. Within this framework, for individuals who like to be in constant motion and do not want to break away from the sources of communication in this process, solutions that can convert the energy of motion into a usable electrical energy for their own needs should be studied. For example, a design has been made which converts the kinetic energy generated by the stress wheel rotation movement into electrical energy by means of a dynamo and enables charging of mobile communication devices directly or via an energy storage unit.

Table 5: Early Years – The organisation for young children LBG

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Primary 7 school children	C1	Why do people hack?	Song composed	A RAP song composed and performed	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/why-do-people-hack	Children in Northern Ireland were thinking of a number of questions to do with HACKING - Who, what, where, how and why? They decided to research some famous hackers to find out the answers to some of their questions. Then they composed and performed a RAP to demonstrate their findings.
Primary 7 school children	C2	How do people find out if fake news is true or false?	Poster	Poster outlining statistics and analysis of the results of the Questionnaire	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/fake-news-true-or-false	Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out how do people know if Fake News is true or false. They collected samples of Fake News to design a survey to test out people's responses. They collected responses from 230 people and the results were analysed and displayed on a results poster. They also developed a PowerPoint outlining how they made a movie around Fake News. It was about a boy who set up a fake website and received lots of views. However, he was caught by his father and his fake online world came to an end!
Primary 7 school children		How do people find out if fake news is true or false?	PowerPoint	PowerPoint detailing the development of a roleplay about Fake News	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/fake-news-true-or-false	Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out how do people know if Fake News is true or false. They collected samples of Fake News to design a survey to test out people's responses. They collected responses from 230 people and the results were analysed and displayed on a results poster. They also developed a PowerPoint outlining how they made a movie around Fake News. It was about

						a boy who set up a fake website and received lots of views. However, he was caught by his father and his fake online world came to an end!
Primary 7 school children		Why do people cyberbully?	Questionnaire	230 Questionnaire - 12 questions Script for Roleplay Video of movie	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/cyberbullying-ni-perspective	Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out why people Cyberbully, If Cyberbullying makes the bully feel good and why they think it is okay to do this. The children developed a questionnaire to circulate to their friends to gather knowledge and understanding of cyberbullying. They also created a movie to highlight the issue of cyberbullying to their school colleagues.

Table 6: Youth for Exchange and Understanding international AISBL’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
YEU	Brave new you - Italian community	How social medias and online platform affect the perceptions of immigrants?	Questionnaire	Questionnaire	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/WYRED%20RESEARCH%20ITALY.pdf	Taking into account all the answers and the currently situation in Italy, we can say that an anti-immigrant movement is rising even in one of the most supporting and welcoming country for refugees. The online world helps people to express and spread their ideas, there are still few controls (which we hope will increase) about what it should be published or not, then people feel free to say everything that is on their mind, by sometimes manipulating information, they can easily hide their personal data and act with an username. We tend to talk a lot online about immigrants, both in a negative and in a positive way (unfortunately less in the second one), but not enough with them. Therefore, a genuine and fruitful online discussion is missing, where different communities can enter in contact and get to know each other better. There is also a need to teach people how to properly use social media and online platforms, as well as how to where to gather information.
YEU	“Mousafir@Greece” project team	How digital platforms can raise awareness,	Case study	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/	LGBT refugees are one of the most discriminated and invisible vulnerable groups of the refugee crisis. Deeply embedded

		<p>understanding and visibility of the LGBT refugees</p>			<p>system/files/GR_Research.pdf</p>	<p>homophobic and transphobic attitudes, often combined with a lack of adequate legal protection against discrimination on grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity, expose many lesbians, gays, bisexuals and transgenders (LGBT) refugees in the receiving countries to violations of their human rights. The lack of visibility, the discrimination and violence against them as well as the mistreatment within their own communities can lead to disastrous results for them and their social environment. Digital platforms can be used by LGBT refugee groups and individuals in order to raise awareness and promote knowledge on the gender dimension of migration. There is an urgent need to identify on an individual basis the situation and the needs of LGBT refugees and act accordingly. Safety as a fundamental human right has to be ensured for LGBT refugees. The institutions and organisations dealing with them should have been properly trained and equipped with knowledge about cultural diversity and gender issues. Regardless of whether LGBT refugees self-identify, service providers have an extraordinary responsibility to ensure they feel safe and welcome in their new communities. The mental health and the development of negative coping mechanisms against the stigma that they bear should be prior concerns of the social and humanitarian projects which aim to provide wellbeing for LGBT refugees. It should be acknowledged that LGBT refugees are often at heightened risk for</p>
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						discrimination and exclusion from access to basic services, and they are also subjected to different forms of abuse, often also by their fellow compatriots. There is a need to highlight the importance and value of digital platforms such as web radios as a tool for humanitarian communication and community empowerment.
Moju Youth Centre	Brave new you-Portuguese community	How social media and online platforms can discourage hateful behaviour among youngsters living in different neighbourhoods?	Questionnaire/interviews	Questionnaire	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/WYRED%20RESEARCH%20Portugal.pdf	Taking into account all the answers received from the questionnaire, we can declare that in Olhao's social neighbourhood young people are victims of online discrimination, which reflects in social exclusion and can lead to psychological problems. The narrative behind all the discriminatory messages, spread mostly through social medias, is based on socio-economic stereotypes. The intention is to make neighbourhood people feel less worthy and lose their dignity. Most of the young people who answered the questionnaire think that the increased use of digital devices for this purpose can encourage hateful behaviour and violent actions among young people. To decrease hate speech level towards the residents of the neighbourhoods and change citizens perspectives on socio-economic stereotypes, more social and cultural activities for young people and their families should be organised. Bringing together people from different areas of the town is a fundamental step, so they can get to know each other and socialise in a safe environment. It will be important to guide some discussions in order

						to create an alternative way to respond to all the verbal and online attacks that people constantly receive. In addition, some activities promoting the respect of human rights and activities should be organised, helping people to get to know each other so they can, by playing, break down some mental stereotypes. Then, in order to trying to prevent hateful speech around us it is essential to teach young people how to use digital devices and online platforms as well as social medias, what should be published and how.
YEU	Brave new you-FYROM/Macedonian community	How social medias and online platforms can break down all the prejudices regarding disabled people in Macedonia?	Case study: online research focused mainly on news, articles and video journals	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/WYRED%20RESEARCH-macedonia.pdf	Taking into account the results of the survey carried out by GfK Institution and the case study of Timijanik, we can state that there is an increase of online and offline discriminatory messages against disabled people, which leads to their social exclusion. People with special needs are something that no one wants to see and live with. This is because it is obviously easier to run away than to try to understand. People are still afraid of something new and different, as a matter of fact, people without disabilities have always tried to ignore others because they do not want to ruin the picture of a “perfect community”. With hate speeches they are trying to send the message that they are not accepted and there is no place for them. As we have seen, the situation is getting worse and worse every day. People still have some stereotypes regarding people with special needs, and especially after the last events with the protests of the

						<p>announcement about the opening of daily care centre for children with special needs in one village in a small municipality in Macedonia. In order to change the view of local communities regarding people with special needs, it is important to create space and time for people to get to know better “their neighbours” and to promote (online and offline) basic human rights. In order to raise the awareness of disability among the population, more information should be spread on online platforms and public events, so as to break down all the prejudices and fake news. Moreover, online training courses should be organised for teachers, volunteers and social assistants who are working with disabled people. It could also be interesting to create online spaces where people can share their work, experiences and exchange information. It could be, also, important to have some online and offline platforms that support disabled people and their families during their “battles”, where they can freely and secretly express their personal experiences and receive some aid, in particular psychological support. Children with disabilities can realise their full potential if society changes the way it sees them and in order to have that change, it could be useful to have an online comprehensive campaign promoting the opening of day-care centres, an inclusive education system, while fighting prejudice against people with disabilities.</p>
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<p>YEU</p>	<p>brave new you - Bosnian Herzegovinian community</p>	<p>How can the use of social media and online platforms contribute to a rise in dialogues among young people from different parts of Bosnia Herzegovina?</p>	<p>Case study</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/WYRED%20RESEARCH-BiH.pdf</p>	<p>According to the current situation in BiH highlighted by the three study cases, we can state that, even if a lot of young people are trying through the use of social media to end discriminatory messages among different ethnics living in the country, there are still rigid ethnical divisions and young people have very few opportunities to meet. In our opinion, it is very important to build a new model of school for future BiH citizens, which is able to promote positive coexistence, without fanning the fire of ethnic hate and suspicion. Through the current “two schools under one roof” system, students’ relationships are complicated by an imbalance in perceptions of power, discriminatory attitudes and economic resources. We argue that the continued separation of youth based on ethnicity hinders the education of future generations for democracy. Regarding the use of online tools and social medias, we can say that it is diverse and reflects the aspiration and believes of the young generation. Indeed, we have on one side young people who are using social media to spread discriminatory and violent messages and videos showing their supposed ethnic superiority. One the other side, there are young people who are using online platforms to mobilise people to act together for one cause forgetting all the past ethnical barriers. We believe that those initiatives should be more promoted through national online campaigns and spread in other medias like radio and televisions and even in public events to</p>
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						increase the audience. Furthermore, we think that more online forums should be created in order to encourage people from different ethnic groups to enter in contact, get to know each other and discuss about their hobbies and passions without fear of being scolded by their parents or being accused of disloyalty by their ethnic community.
YEU	Brave new you - Kosovar community	How does the online representation of RAE (Roma, Ashkali, Egyptian) people impact their future for good education and jobs?	Research	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/Kosovo%20Research.pdf	Taking into account the current situation described above, we can state that nowadays, RAE communities, despite having played an important part in Kosovo's society, are being discriminated against and emarginated from society. The exclusion takes place in both, offline and online settings, and decreases the possibility to have access to good education and to find a job. The situation is getting worse with the increase of online videos, photos and messages which highlight the stereotypes of RAE communities and make it difficult for them to be considered and to feel part of the society. As a result, young people feel discriminated against and not welcome in public places, like in schools or in city parks. They lose their self-esteem, they underestimate their work possibilities and they end up increasing the divisions, already present in the society, since they give up integrating by living all the entire life within their own ethnic community. For this reason, it is important for all citizens to cooperate in inclusion activities, online and offline anti-hate speeches projects and raise the current

						<p>issues of RAE communities. There should be more non-formal activities based on a series of counter-narratives to approach the problem, to try to integrate these communities in our society. We think that it could be important to start an online campaign with the aim to give more visibility to RAE communities in Kosovo, highlight their qualities and values and break down all the prejudices against them. In addition, it could be interesting to create online forums and platforms where young people of Kosovo can freely discuss, change their opinions, ideas and knowledge. This way, young people of RAE communities will have the possibility to share among young people of other communities their cultures and let others know about important historical RAE figures, currently famous people followed in particularly by young people, such as youtubers, writers, singers, actors and actresses. The final goal is to show that these communities can participate and contribute to Kosovo's society and increase the spread of online positive comments and posts regarding RAE young people. In order to increase the online presence of these groups, we should focus more on the education of digital skills for young people. It is fundamental that they are aware of the advantages of using internet and the numerous things that can be done with online applications, which are useful for personal development, to know how to gather a variety of information, discover future jobs</p>
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						and important topics, such as the creation of online applications for future jobs.
YEU	Brave new you-Serbian community	How can online sources and media support the perspective of young people and support the integration of communities like the Roma?	Research	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/Serbia%20Research.pdf	<p>Taking into account the situation described above, we can state that young Roma are victims of online and offline discrimination and that all the efforts to integrate them into the society have not yet been successful. Roma communities are not a new problem for Serbian inhabitants; however, the young population has a skewed point of view of them given by their environment. Young people believe that a Roma is a thief, is lazy and is “bad company”. For these reasons, it is important to change the mind of Serbian youths, fight against the stereotypes, focus on the integration of Roma with Serbian youth through a mix of activities and online tools. In order to fight this social problem, it is fundamental to promote differences and shared values, encourage multicultural dialogues between Roma youth and youngsters from the mainstream population. By providing the opportunity for online and offline interaction between the two sides, Roma can be integrated in everyday social life of the mainstream population. The main aim is to challenge youth to take into consideration the obstacles and difficulties Roma face, to ensure young people understand that we are all humans and not defined by race, ethnicity, religion and physical appearance. Since the internet is a big tool for information and communication, it is essential to create online</p>

						<p>spaces in favour of Roma. For example, a creation of a YouTube channel to show interviews with a member of this group, who could explain the situation in which they currently live, their stories, their dreams for the future or how they can help to change their role in the Serbian society. Another idea to facilitate the integration of Roma in the society is the creation of online forums, where different people could write about their experiences with Roma, focusing on youths it could be also an interesting activity which stimulates the dialogue between the two communities and break down all the prejudices. Online forums have usually a big impact since they create a positive, safe and judgment-free environment for youth to discuss and share their opinions and experiences with peers from other communities. In addition, in order to answer to all the discriminatory videos and pictures published online against Roma, it could be useful to create an online campaign fighting against fake news in websites which usually write about the problems that Roma people generate to the Serbian community. Through the online campaign, only correct and official information will be spread, making Serbs aware of the real situation, thus giving the opportunity to young Roma to speak and to be heard by society.</p>
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<p>YEU</p>	<p>Brave new you- Turkish community</p>	<p>How are gender roles, assigned to people through social norms, reflected in and perceived by young people through digital channels?</p>	<p>focus group technique: interviews + survey</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/TR%20research.pdf</p>	<p>The patriarchal social order in Turkey and gender inequality based on the roles that people have been subjected to since they were born are troubling issues for youth. As people normalise this, this belief and its consequences will spread more and more as time passes by. According to this, gender includes not only gender differences, but also unequal power relations between sexes. The roles we take, the jobs we do, our posture, our words are due to the gender roles which have been constructed and developed for ages. The roles we take usually dictate where we should stand, what we should wear, when we should talk or be quiet, which job we should choose, how we react to events or things. Women who are mostly affected negatively are the most disadvantaged group. These roles, though, put pressure not only on women but also on men. The lifestyle which forces men to be macho and masculine makes them brutal, strict, and prone to violence. Gender inequities and employment discrimination continue in education, politics, law enforcement, business, medicine, media, the military and religion. Creative contributions of women are less encouraged and recognised than those of men in many areas, such as the arts and sciences. Women still suffer negative effects of discrimination in quality of life outcomes related to their safety and employment and leadership of government and business organisations. Females, more than males, are victims of sexual harassment. There are few</p>
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						<p>women leaders or top officials especially in national politics, even though their stereotyped strengths for being less likely to be influenced by corruption and more likely to advance peace and cooperation are desired by all. The authors have noted that individuals should realise that their jobs and their posture do not define their gender. This is the reason why we would like to tackle this gender inequality issue that we face all the time in our daily life. There should be increased public understanding and media attention related to gender equity in education. Special focus has to be given to projects which will aim to show in all persons in equal and non-stereotyped manner, fully respecting their personality and human dignity. Online and offline media should show positive examples of non-discrimination and respect of human rights in both private and public aspects of life and should raise awareness on equal participation of women and men in economic and social development. Policies should be created in order to eliminate sexism, gender-phobia, homophobia, bi-phobia, trans-phobia and other prejudice and stereotypes. Organisations and institutions should promote equal participation and representation of persons with different sexual orientation and gender identity to decision-making positions in society.</p>
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YEU	Brave new you - Slovenian community	Do online sources support fear and hate towards refugees?	Research	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/Slovenia%20WYRED%20Research%2017.08.31.pdf	<p>Taking into account the situation described above, we can declare that in Slovenia, online information is oriented in supporting fear and hate towards immigrants, in particular Syrian refugees. Asylum seekers who live in Slovenia or just across the national territory to continue their travel are negatively represented in online as well as in offline platforms. The increase of discriminatory messages and posts on social medias, particularly on Facebook, is followed through by racist attitudes in daily life. Most Slovenians are angry about the way the government is dealing with the situation and they use digital devices to express all their frustrations and sadness. However, it is important to notice that the direct addressee of all the messages spread online are not the members of the government, but the refugees who are not responsible for the current social and economic situation in Slovenia. In any case, they are the ones who are suffering as they are the victims of violent and discriminatory messages. We think that more activities should be organised based on non-formal education with the aim to teach young people to distinguish fake news from real news. The main objective should be to change people's stubborn view on refugees. In order to do that, more unbiased and factual information, based on official channels, should be spread online together with videos showing the reality of present and past situations. This way, we will prove to Slovenian citizens that Slovenia already had</p>
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						<p>problems before immigrants started to arrive, therefore refugees are not responsible for them. Citizens are afraid of immigrants simply because they do not know them, they are afraid of the unknown. In order to break down all the prejudices against immigrants and the ignorance towards them, we think that it is important to share more posts, messages and videos online, showing all the good qualities and values of immigrants. Videos that show them as human beings and not numbers, videos which take into account their life and all the benefits that immigrant can bring to the Slovenian community. Our main goal is that through the increase of the online representation of immigrants, Slovenian citizens start looking at them just as human beings with their own religion and culture. We want to make sure that when they come to our country, they will be accepted and have all human rights just like us. In order to reach all these goals, it is important to create online platforms where refugees and Slovenian citizens can interact and get to know each other better. We think that, in order to have more impact, it could be great if young people created an online campaign in favour of refugees shared across the national territory, showing what they can offer to the country.</p>
YEU	Brave new you - Azerbaijani community	Discrimination caused by clothing in Azerbaijan and the role of social media	Qualitative approach Interviews	Research	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/AZ_Research.pdf	Azerbaijan is a secular country, without official laws stipulating what citizens should wear. People should wear whatever they want and at the same time feel comfortable in their

						<p>clothes. However, unfortunately most of our population still lives according to outdated standards of dressing and thinks that girls should wear long dresses that cover all parts of the body, and men wear only black clothes. As a result, young people with modern views of the world are forced to wear what society wants them to wear and not go beyond these standards; otherwise they will face shame and judgment in public places. It is well known that restrictions on freedom of expression, part of which is the right to choose your own clothing, can restrict people's creativity and individuality. Stereotypes, prejudices and discrimination based on clothing should be overcome. It should become a general belief that the clothes one chooses to wear and the fashion one chooses to follow should not affect their social standing. In order to raise social awareness on this particular issue and to encourage people to become more open-minded, it is recommended to develop and implement projects in school which tackle the issue of the right to freedom of expression. Social media could play a positive role and help people disseminate their unique dressing choices alongside with their character and personality. Petitions, campaigns and events through social media for the right against discrimination and self-expression should be encouraged and spread. Employers should be adequately informed and trained so as not to judge future employees based on dress codes.</p>
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<p>YEU</p>	<p>Brave new you- Cypriot community</p>	<p>How does the media affect the attempts to achieve social cohesion between the two communities in Cyprus?</p>	<p>Survey+ research</p>	<p>Survey + Research</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/system/files/CY_Research.pdf</p>	<p>The findings of the questionnaire show a universal agreement that the media, whether traditional or social, play a very important role to the way the two communities see each other and, as a result, to achieving social cohesion on the island of Cyprus. This role becomes even more important when talking about two communities who have been at war other only 45 years ago. Traditional local media are seen as more old-fashioned, with organisational structures and/or ownership that can be manipulated due to their political or community affiliation. Their audience is primarily older generations from the communities. On the other hand, social media are seen as freer platform to express ideas and report news without the burden of the past. Social media are used mostly by younger generations who are free from older beliefs and hatred. Their citizen journalism through social media is seen as more objective and more geared towards a common future between the two communities. Last but not least, social media users are using primarily English language, thus making their online content immediately available to both communities, unlike the local media which broadcast in national languages. Although there was widespread agreement on the primacy of traditional media (tv, radio, print) on the island of Cyprus, digital content and new technologies have undoubtedly started to change the media landscape so profoundly that the group recommended more expansive</p>
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						<p>consideration in a range of areas. There is a need to respect the past but, at the same time, for both communities to start looking forward, using their respective youth and their use of social media as a driving force. For local media especially, a wider and deeper regulation of the media landscape is needed for a positive change towards more social cohesion. Hate speech can be greatly reduced by means of legislative regulation. More common bi-communal and bi-lingual projects could ease tensions between the two communities and, thus, enhance mutual understanding. Bicommunal events and/or events that push for positive change should be further promoted through the power of social media. At the same time, celebrations of past events that brought devastation and pain to the other side, e.g. conflict memorial days, need to stop. Without proper regulation at national policy level and a concerted effort by local and traditional media, social change will continue at the very low levels we see today.</p>
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Table 7: Moves' artefacts list

Organisation	Project Leads	Research Questions	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	Maximilian Katzengruper	How does our environmental future look like?	Creative work	Digital collage linked to YouTube	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/environmental-and-renewable-energies/project/our-environmental-future	Wouldn't it be great when our world looked like the symbolic picture for the environment project? In fact, we are far away from there. Big countries dissolve international agreements on climate change, other countries do not fulfil, what promised with regard to the reduction of CO2 emissions, there are even persons arguing that the climate change as nothing but a lie. How can they? It is our planet and our future! The following (digital) collage brings together some information on environmental issues and links the project to the YouTube-Video "Dear Future Generations: Sorry". Should

						be seen by every decision maker in the field.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	juliahackl, steffiholzer, alinasalomon	Why should we protect animals?	creative work	text "written" by a dog	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/animal-protection	In a short text Romca - a dog - explains that it is a living being, having the right to be treated properly by humans. A list of organisations still using animals for different experiments is shown.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	kerstin.chm, sophie 26, leasal	How can food waste be prevented?	Text	Appeal to the European Commission	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/waste-food-appeal-eu	To deal with this problem, we suggest to the members of the parliament to: 1) explain to consumers that the expiration date does not mean, that the product is no longer consumable, but still - even for a long time after the best before date - can be eaten: The expiration date is no reason to throw away food! 2) Food waste is massively given, when especially

						vegetables and fruits are sorted out, just because they do not fit to European norms. These products could be offered for cheaper prices to persons of lower economic status.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	lisa lewisch, NadineKroisser, schnabifo, MelanieWeidenauer	How can stress be prevented in schools?	creative work	Radio interviews on stress	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/stress/project/radio-firnberg-interview-stress	Young people are taking over the roles of experts in the topic of stress and are asked in a radio interview (mp3) how stress can be dealt with in everyday life.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	Celina Felkl, simon.fruehlingere, Amrit	Does the school system fail us?	Creative work	poem	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-	The school system needs to be changed. It is not changing at all though urgently needed. Education does not nourish rather it turns out to be an unhealthy place where anxiety and sleepless nights are normal. Young peoples' worth is defined by grades and not by being they themselves.

					austria/project/school-it	They want to learn, but the system detains them from doing so. In the following poem it is made clear that changes are urgently needed.
Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen	jasmin28, Anastasia...,patricksti	How will digital implants influence our future?	creative work	poem	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/digital-implants	This is a poem about the dangers of digital implants. For animals, especially for dogs, it is common practice to implant RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) chips, in order to easily identify them when getting lost. Humans use implants in the size of rice grains for an "easy" way to open car-, house or office-doors, for e-banking, to access the mobile or to provide medical data in case of emergency. These chips are not too expensive and can even be implemented in a piercing-studio. But do we really want a future like that?

<p>Hertha-Firnberg-Schulen</p>	<p>Anna, Julia_Stummer</p>	<p>The positive and the negative effects tourism can bring</p>	<p>Internet research</p>	<p>scientific test</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/hertha-firnberg-gruppe-austria/project/tourism-china</p>	<p>Did you know that in 2016 China accounted for 21% of the world's spending on tourism? This text deals with the fact that tourism can bring many economic and social benefits, particularly in rural areas and developing countries, but mass tourism is also associated with negative effects. Tourism can only be sustainable if it is carefully managed so that potential negative effects on the host community and the environment are not permitted to outweigh the financial benefits. Find out more in the text attached!</p>
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Table 8: Boundaries observatory C.I.C's artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Brit School	Maya, Arlie, Kammie, Jordanne	Gender Equality	Presentation	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Maya, Arlie, Kammie, Jordanne	Gender Equality	Discussion	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Beth, Shannon, Courtney, Maryanne, Eliza	Male Emotions Online	Presentation	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Beth, Shannon, Courtney, Maryanne, Eliza	Male Emotions Online	Discussion	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Cavan, Labbie, Muhith, Emma, Marquise	Life Hacks	Presentation	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Cavan, Labbie, Muhith, Emma, Marquise	Life Hacks	Discussion	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details

Brit School	Dani, Amy, Jodie, Jas, Emma	Influencers	Presentation	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Dani, Amy, Jodie, Jas, Emma	Influencers	Discussion	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details
Brit School	Dani, Amy, Jodie, Jas, Emma	Influencers	Reflection	Video File	Uploaded	See WYRED platform for details

Table 9: Tel Aviv University’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Inclusion and gender	Poster	Summary of discussions	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/inclusion-and-gender	The students of The Summer Youth University were taking the summer semester during very interesting days; the LGBT community was protesting - demanding equal surrogacy rights for gay men. Tens of thousands of men and women came to Tel Aviv’s Rabin Square to protest and back the community – and the issue became prominent in Israeli society. The young students felt the need to talk about inclusion.
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	The refugees’ problem and the future	Poster	Futures wheel	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/refugees-problem-and-future	The students of Tel Aviv Summer University took a tour to the south of Tel Aviv city – where a lot of disadvantaged communities live. They learned about problems of the refugee’, the newcomers to the neighbourhood, and of the host population. Using the future wheel method, which they have practiced while being led by Dr. Tal Soffer, head of the unit for technology and society foresight (TSF) at Tel Aviv University, they tried to understand what the expression of the problem in the future would be.
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Segregation versus understanding	Poster	Futures wheel	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/segregation-	Like some of their colleagues, the members of this team (young high school students, who came to Tel Aviv university in order to take the summer semester), also chose to deal with the idea of "The 4 Israeli tribes" – the four main cultural groups that Israel is disintegrating into:

					<p><u>versus- understanding</u></p>	<p>the ultra-Orthodox Jews, the national religious Jewish sector, the Arab sector and the secular Jewish sector. The young students came from different sectors, from cities and villages in the social and geographic periphery of Israel. Trying to find a way to deliver the message that "we are different, but we are also the same", the students wanted to figure out what are the various implications of this issue, nowadays and in the future. They have used a future wheel to analyse the different aspects of the segregation between Arabs and Jews.</p>
<p>TAU Summer Youth University</p>	<p>Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University</p>	<p>Sustainability and environment-future wheel</p>	<p>Poster</p>	<p>Futures wheel</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/sustainability-and-environment-future-wheel</p>	<p>These young students of the Tel Aviv youth university - a project that enables high school students from Israel's geographic periphery, most of whom are the first in their families who enrol in higher education - to have an academic semester at Tel Aviv University, were concerned about our environment. However, they were also inspired by their research tour, in which they saw a variety of solutions both at the Faculty of Environmental Studies at Tel Aviv University and on the roof of one of Tel Aviv's big malls - two buildings that implement principles of sustainability. They also have discussed the issue with Prof. Colin Price, the head of the Porter School of Environmental Studies. As a part of their research, the young students have used the "future wheel" method, which they have learned during a lecture with Dr. Tal Soffer, trying to foresight the implications and the consequence of the environment problems.</p>

TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	The socio-economic gap	Poster	Summary of discussions	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/socio-economic-gap	<p>On their educational tour from the poverty of south Tel Aviv to the high-tech and the most developed and rich part of the city, the students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to have an academical semester in the university - decided to deal with the social-economic gap. **In the picture: Tel Aviv, bottom-up, rags to riches: the building of Facebook Israel, as caught from street level by the camera of one young guide during the tour** The members of this team, from Tel Aviv Youth University, have tried to use the "future wheel" tool to identify the implications of the socio-economic gap, but found it very confusing, so Dr. Tal Soffer, head of The unit for technology and society foresight (TSF) at Tel Aviv University, came to help – engaging a very interesting discussion about the need to talk about technology while we are learning about the future.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	The "4 Israeli tribes" - tolerance and cleavages between the Israeli groups	Poster	Futures wheel	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/4-israeli-tribes-tolerance-and-cleavages-between	<p>The members of this team, from Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to have an academical semester in the university, were inspired by a lecture discussing the idea of "The 4 Israeli tribes" - a phrase that was coined by the President of Israel to modify a four groups that Israel is disintegrating into: the ultra-Orthodox, the national religious, the Arab sector and the secular Jewish sector. The young students, Arabs and Jews, religious and secular, who succeeded in bridging the gaps and</p>

						disagreements - studying and living together - wanted to express the idea that there is another way. As a part of their study, the students have used a "future wheel" in order to identify the various implications of this issue, aiming to analyse the implications of the technology and information society on these vectors:
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Education for refugee children	Video	A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) & a short commercial: https://youtu.be/keUfo2mr vBo	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/children-refugees	The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society. Representing the young generation perspective, they pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. As part of the research, using a "futures wheel" method, the student assumed that robots would do the routine jobs and therefore there won't be enough jobs left for migrants, who have inappropriate skills. Therefore, the children of the refugees should have the same education as the Israelis, otherwise they will be pushed into a life of poverty and even crime. Following these assumptions, the group chose to deal with the issue of education for refugee children. During the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision

						<p>makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Tolerance towards people from different cultures	Video	<p>they used a mock-up tool to present an idea for a mobile app https://youtu.be/xv_9Ef0eR9g & A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) &</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/peaceful-coexistence-between-different-religions</p>	<p>The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society. Representing the young generation perspective, they pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. The young students believed that they should be an example of peaceful coexistence between different religions and culture - Arabs and Jews, religious and secular - that succeeded in bridging the gaps and disagreements, studying and living together. Thus, they wanted to express the idea that there is another way and argued that people should meet each other (online and offline) and share their common hobbies and interests in order to be more tolerant to other people from different cultures. Thus, they have decided to try creating a mobile app that should help connect between teens based on their common hobbies and interests.</p>

						<p>During the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act. They have described their main tool – the mobile app, explained the vision using a mock-up tool. You can watch the presentation that was given during the graduation ceremony to a wide audience including senior representatives from the Israeli Ministry of Education, researchers from Tel Aviv University, visitors from the third sector, educators and the families of the participants (Hebrew).</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Accessibility of higher education	Brochure, poster	A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) &	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/accessibility-higher-education	<p>The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society. Representing the young generation perspective, they pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. Based on their "learning journey" and the attempt to explore</p>

						<p>different aspects of life in the future, the students have realized that education plays an important role in. They claimed that today there are many solutions that overcome distance problems and accessibility of higher education, but there is not enough publicity for them. They decided to try to find a solution. During the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act. Then they started to build a site about higher education programs which are available for youth in Israel.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	"The 4 Israeli tribes"-bridging the gaps and disagreements	Brochure, poster	A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) & poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/bridging-gaps-and-disagreements	<p>The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University, representing the young generation perspective, pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. During their "journey of learning" they were inspired by a lecture discussing the idea of "The 4 Israeli tribes" - a phrase that was coined by the President of Israel to modify a four groups that</p>

						<p>Israel is disintegrating into: the ultra-Orthodox, the national religious, the Arab sector and the secular Jewish sector. Using their experience of living and working in the digital world, the students claim that social networks are catalysts for hate speech but can also be a promoter of social change. In the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act. The students decided to outline a program for a blog which will describe their experiences in the project where Arabs and Jews, religious and secular, succeeded in bridging the gaps and disagreements - studying and living together.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Sustainability and environment	Brochure, poster	A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) & poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/green-campus	Using the futures wheel's results, the students argued that sustainability is an important goal, and youngsters, leaders and stakeholders should be convinced about the need to promote it. The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society. Representing the young generation perspective, they pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers,

						<p>locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. Using the futures wheel's results, the students argued that sustainability is an important goal, and youngsters, leaders and stakeholders should be convinced about the need to promote it. Therefore, they chose to create a campaign that would promote sustainability. During the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act. They had decided to launch a campaign across the Tel Aviv Campus area, and they tried to use Instagram in order to deliver their message.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	Tolerance and gender	Video	A "brief" document for their campaign (that includes summary of discussions) & a short	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/equals	The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society. Representing the young generation perspective, they pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a

				commercial: https://youtu.be/xwzrlgAECg8		<p>journey of learning and researching various problems related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects. The young students were discussing gender issues. They were inspired by the Israeli LGBT community's protest - demanding equal surrogacy rights for gay men - and asked: "Why are we being indoctrinated to use stereotypes from an early age?" They have decided to deliver the message "No one has the right to tell me whom to love". During the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more. With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act.</p>
TAU Summer Youth University	Instructors from Tel Aviv Youth University	A special presentation of the WYRED project	Video		https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/special-presentation-wyred-project	<p>A major milestone for The Tel Aviv Summer University program was achieved as the young students presented their projects in their graduation ceremony. The program was led by Dr. Tal Soffer, head of The unit for technology and society foresight (TSF) at Tel Aviv University, and the Youth Summer University's staff. The students were exposed to various issues related to the digital society in the present and in the future, focusing on the Israeli society. It was done through various tours in relevant</p>

						<p>places and lectures about different subjects. Following that, the students were asked to identify a problem that would be important in the year 2030, to explore it, analyse, and propose creative solutions that will engage with large audiences and reach the decision makers. The work was done in teams where the students could express their opinion in a moderated dialog. During the graduation ceremony the WYRED project was presented, and the students showcased their projects to a wide audience including (no: necessary) senior representatives from the Israeli Ministry of Education, researchers from Tel Aviv University, visitors from the third sector, educators and the families of the participants. You can have a small glimpse of two scenes video clip from one of the team projects, which deals with the refugees issue: (Shown in the picture above : The young students are standing in front of a slide that says "Thank you" in a special font that combines letters in Hebrew and Arabic).</p>
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5. LIST OF PROJECTS CYCLE 3

Table 10: Doga Schools' artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Hamitler Doga Schools	EE AND CO	How do you use technology in your daily life? Which apps do you use to talk with your friends?	Research paper, project report	Project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/influencers-social-media/project/nomophobia-levels-secondary-school-students	The project was run by YP to see nomophobia levels of teachers, they were quite surprised at the results. The goal is to allow teachers to take control of their own telephone dependency. The project was run by YP to see nomophobia levels of teachers, they were quite surprised at the results. The goal is to allow teachers to take control of their own telephone dependency.
Çamlıca Doga Schools	BE	Do you buy your things in online shops?	Research short video	Mp4	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/influencers-social-media/project/follow-social-media-influencer-t%C3%BClay-g%C3%B6k%C3%A7imen	The project was run by YP to see what they felt and thought each day in response to the influencer's posts. They then reflected on how the influencers were influencing them. The influencers on social media make young people feel good or feel left out. It shows that their posts influence young people's purchasing behaviours, their feelings for others as well as their relationships. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Kadıköy Doga Schools	ZİD AND DF	Do you buy your things in online shops?	Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/influencers-social-	The project was run by YP to see impact of social media on depression. They were quite surprised at the results. They realised the impact

					<u>media/project/impact-social-media-depression-tendency</u>	of social media on human life is one of the important issues that need to be studied more scientifically. The duration of social media usage, the purposes for which social media contributions are shared and the responses to the posts do have a significant impact on users. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair
İncek Doga Schools	ASE AND AY	Have you observed how adults around you use the apps?	Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/influencers-social-media/project/relationship-between-use-social-media-use-and-narcisism</u>	The project was run by YP to see if there was a recognisable relationship between the use of social media and narcissism. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çekmeköy Doga Schools	İİB	Have you observed how adults around you use the apps?	Survey project, project report	Survey project, project report	<u>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/influencers-social-media/project/social-media-impact-young-people-how-do-you-feel-without</u>	The project was run by YP to research social media impact. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair

Büyükçekmece	BA AND SK	Do you know which is a stereotype?	Survey project, project report	Survey project, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/dont-stay-silent-investigation-impact	The project was run by YP to examine the impact of a patriarchal social structure on women's social lives. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	YP13	Do you know which is a stereotype?	Social Responsibility Project poster	Poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-inequality	The project was run by YP to draw attention to gender inequality. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	YP14	Stereotypes are true when they start to play?	Tech Design Prototype	Prototype	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/best-female-characters-literature	The project was run by YP to draw attention to female characters in literature. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Çamlıca Doga Schools	SK AND AZH	Stereotypes are true when they start to play?	Tech Design Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/changes-about-names-female-characters	The project was run by YP to determine whether the naming of female characters and the writing styles of the authors during the period between 1830 and 1960 were bringing female characters to life in a particular way. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In

						addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Bodrum Doga Schools	NK AND GK	Do you think that people from different cultures perceive stereotypes in the same way than you?	Tech Design Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/image-woman-redefined-didem-madaks-poems	The project was run by YP to hear about the female figure in literature we heard for years from a male voice, but from a female poet and thus to see the different expressions of the female figure. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	YP15	Who is watching us and how are we watching each other?	Research Presentation with video	Presentation with video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/what-bullying	The project was run by YP to draw attention to bullying and similar behaviours. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	YP16	Who is watching us and how are we watching each other?	Research Presentation with video	Presentation with video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/bullying	The project was run by YP to draw attention to bullying and ways to fight it. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Ataşehir 1 Doga Schools	ASK	Who is watching us and how are we watching each other?	Survey project, project report	Survey project, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/effect-	The project was run by YP to analyse the impact of gaming on mathematical achievement. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In

					<u>technological-playing-time</u>	addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Hatay Doga Schools	BEE	What are these terms and conditions that we agree to everyday?	Tech Design Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/technology-standing-against-sense-time	The project was run by YP to see how the impact and challenges of technology develop across time. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Gaziosmanpaşa Doga Schools	YKM AND YC	What are these terms and conditions that we agree to everyday?	Survey project, project report	Survey project, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/impact-technology-use-individual	The project was run by YP to analyse the impact of technology on social relationships. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Bayrampaşa Doga Schools	ASK AND GP	Are you doing something in order to reach this point that you and/or society deem “perfect”? What conscious or even unconscious impact do you think this idea of the “perfect”	Tech Design Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/self-image-online/project/what-would-i-do	The project was run by YP to identify and analyse empathy among high school students. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.

		person has on people?				
Batışehir Doga Schools	CK	What are the challenges of technology for disabled people?	Tech Design Prototype; project presentation	Prototype; project presentation	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/fire-sensor-visually-hearing-impaired	The project was run by YP to create a fire sensor for the visually and hearing impaired. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	YP17	Do you think that people from different cultures perceive stereotypes in the same way than you	Social Responsibility Newsletter	Newsletter	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-equality	The project was run by YP to draw attention to gender inequality. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Bayrampaşa Doga Schools	ZDK AND SK	How did migration in our country affect air pollution, water pollution etc. and what can we do about that?	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/doga-community/project/impact-migration-society-and-opinions-refugees-syrian-example	The project was run by YP to analyse the impact of migration on society and the opinions of refugees. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çekirge Doga Schools	IO AND YS	Are there stereotypes on the internet?	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/different	The project was run by YP to identify the representation of women in folk songs of the Bursa region. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out

					-view-folk-songs-%E2%80%9Cwomen%E2%80%9D-traces	across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çiğli Doga Schools	EUM	Where is the place of technology?	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/impact-technology-values-interaction-project	The project was run by YP to see impact of technology on values. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çiğli Doğa Schools	IT	How did migration of refugees change the population?	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/impact-migration-communities-and-individuals	The project was run by YP to analyse the impact of migration on communities and individuals. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Florya Doga Schools	IS	What is the impact of technology on academic success?	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/raising-awareness-violence-against-children-and-study-raise	The project was run by YP to discover awareness of violence against children. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Halkalı Doga Schools	LB AND SE	What kind of career are you planning by	Survey, project report	Survey, project report	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-	The project was run by YP to identify future jobs in order to promote informed career choices.

		taking future jobs in hand?			community/project/defining-future-jobs-and-career-choices	The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Marmara University	AMT	Have you observed how adults around you use the apps?	Survey project, video	Survey project, video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/your-lives-social-media-vs-adults	The project was run by YP to identify differences between the life on social media of young people and their parents. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	IA	How can we be more active participants within our democracies?	Survey project, video	Survey project, video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/digital-participation/project/paris-principles-14-images	The project was run by YP Paris principles. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences.
Çamlıca Religious High School for Girls	ESD AND BE	How can we be more active participants within our democracies?	Survey project, video	Survey project, video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/digital-participation/project/dictatorship	The project was run by YP to define differences between dictatorship and democracy. The artefact was published on a WYRED community and this project was carried out across different European countries to see whether there are similarities or differences. In addition to this, students submitted their projects to the TÜBITAK student fair.

Table 11: Youth for Exchange and Understanding international AISBL’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
N/A	N/A	Can Instagram promote a positive perception of the body?	Research	Word document.	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1882602184	The research investigated the role of ‘body-positive’ online movement in challenging the mainstream vision of perfect body. The evidence produced show the potential benefits of body positive contents on women self-acceptance and self-esteem: young women who viewed positive contents on Instagram felt more satisfied with their physical aspect.
N/A	N/A	Can social Media provide Mental Health Support?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1942364750	The research focused on the positive impact that social media can have on mental health, particularly on the role that online peer support communities play in supporting people in need.
N/A	N/A	How can the educational system tackle gender inequality?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908406377	The research explored the most pressing gender disparities in education and identified possible solutions by presenting a case study of a British primary school
N/A	N/A	Women and entrepreneurship. What measures to unlock their potential?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2015486721	The research investigated the obstacles found by women in accessing to the business world and show the high economical return of investments in gender equality

N/A	N/A	Can cyberbullying be stopped by involving young people in the fight against it?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/1933356618	The research studied how to address online bullying with a young people-centred approach, based on a real programme implemented in the U.S.
N/A	N/A	Treating BDD over the internet: is it possible?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/2005392330	The research analysed the consequences on the mental health of the massive exposure to unrealistic beauty standards and examined the positive effects of internet-based online therapies.
N/A	N/A	Excessive use of internet and anxiety: a possible correlation?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/2013754036	The research focused on the positive impact that social media can have on mental health, particularly in raising awareness around wellbeing and support people in need.
N/A	N/A	Can media literacy improve civic engagement?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/1950368141	Through the case study of Cyber Seniors, a programme that provide digital assistance to senior citizens, the research shows the impact of media literacy on civic engagement
N/A	N/A	Learn media literacy through Gamification: a feasible solution?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/1999078077	The research shows how the integration of Gamification approach in education guarantees a better learning experience for students and therefore contributes in fighting disinformation and fake news.
N/A	N/A	Can digital tools make democracy more representative?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/1923453490	Taking ‘Better neighbourhood’ case as an example, the research demonstrates how e-democracy platform can promote civic engagement.

N/A	N/A	Can social media be blamed for the rise in narcissism?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908997727	<p>Modern society, also through the use of social media, encourages individuality to the detriment of real community bonds. We can say that we are officially in the era of narcissism, which we could also define as "digital narcissism". Embracing a certain degree of narcissism creates a urge to feel special and above all helps to maintain a healthy sense of self-esteem: therefore it is essential to have a clear distinction between unhealthy narcissism and healthy narcissism. From the data in the literature we cannot state that the use of social media leads to an increase in the Narcissistic Personality Disorder, but certainly they have been demonstrated by different researches that social media websites encourage self-promotion and therefore could be strengthened, even if indirectly, some narcissistic traits of the person.</p> <p>"It is important to remember that these are only correlations, however," said Jessica McCain, "This is not evidence that social media causes narcissism or vice versa. Theoretically, we suspect that individuals with pre-existing narcissism are drawn to social media, but the present evidence only establishes that the two are related."</p>
N/A	N/A	Is online self-presentation correlated with self-esteem?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1950706568	<p>Modern society, also through the use of social media, encourages individuality to the detriment of real community bonds. We can say that we are officially in the era of narcissism, which we could also define as "digital narcissism". Embracing a certain</p>

						<p>degree of narcissism creates a urge to feel special and above all helps to maintain a healthy sense of self-esteem: therefore it is essential to have a clear distinction between unhealthy narcissism and healthy narcissism. From the data in the literature we cannot state that the use of social media leads to an increase in the Narcissistic Personality Disorder, but certainly they have been demonstrated by different researches that social media websites encourage self-promotion and therefore could be strengthened, even if indirectly, some narcissistic traits of the person.</p> <p>"It is important to remember that these are only correlations, however," said Jessica McCain, "This is not evidence that social media causes narcissism or vice versa. Theoretically, we suspect that individuals with pre-existing narcissism are drawn to social media, but the present evidence only establishes that the two are related."</p>
N/A	N/A	Can education eradicate gender stereotypes?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908998811	<p>A first way to overcome stereotypes is to offer accurate information on the subject of the stereotype: at school, this could mean discussing together starting from newspaper articles, scientific research and other data that are perceived as reliable.</p> <p>A second path to overcome stereotypes is to empathize with the "victim" subjects to the same stereotype: reading and documenting is always a good way to empathize with cultures and people different from us and thus overcome stereotypes</p>

N/A	N/A	Gender and Disney princesses: good role models?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1984671067	<p>It was interesting to analyse how, with the times, the image of the woman has radically changed: each princess has brought with her a brick that, little by little, has helped to create characters increasingly rich in human and emancipated qualities.</p> <p>The stereotypical figure of women has undergone an evolution in Disney cartoons, which can be seen by comparing the first animated films (which date back to the first decades of the 90s) with the more modern ones. The message conveyed in the most recent cartoons coincides with an attempt to overcome the stereotyping of the female figure as a beautiful character, perfect and at the same time subordinate to her destiny to become a bride and therefore to be realized as a woman.</p> <p>The feminine image changes definitively, going from the scarce, even if present, efforts of autonomy of the princesses of the 80s, to the complete and total autarchy of protagonists like Mulan. Finally the woman takes her life in hand and renounces every type of male-dominated and misogynist slavery, saving, as in the case of the Chinese champion, not only her existence but also that of the much venerated male characters, finally proving to the world that the female gender everything has the same capabilities and the same weaknesses as the male ones.</p>
N/A	N/A	Is it possible to prevent the spread of harmful behaviour	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1984671067	Education regarding the use of the web is today an essential duty for every teacher and

		towards teenagers on the Internet?			3/buckets/2313524/uploads/1924120385	<p>parent attentive to the needs and the potential but also to the fragility of the adolescents who massively use the Internet and live immersed in this reality, which is part of their world and it is an instrument with which they define themselves and the context that surrounds them. In a society like that, current cyberbullying behaviours turn into a show with thousands of spectators. Prevention of cyberbullying situations is possible especially with good information and education that must be provided by the main reference areas for adolescents: the family and the school.</p> <p>Training should be aimed not only at pupils (potential victims), but also at teachers and non-teaching staff in schools, with the aim of creating a school environment that discourages bullying and sensitizing educational staff to recognition and commissioning acts of adequate responses to bullying</p>
N/A	N/A	How do cybersecurity measures protect users and the system?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1984614727	<p>Faced with increasingly targeted and destructive cyber-attacks, classic antiviruses are no longer enough to protect the security perimeter of companies: it is important to use new systems based on the analysis of behaviour over time of the endpoints which, thanks to the use of advanced algorithms of artificial intelligence for cyber defence, they can understand if a machine has been infected by analysing any anomalous behaviour.</p> <p>Artificial intelligence allows us to process more data than human capabilities. He can do</p>

						<p>it in a short time, learning as he digests data thanks to machine learning.</p> <p>No computer system is completely waterproof. Therefore, when an attack occurs, reacting promptly is decisive. Because more time means more data exposed and, potentially, greater risk (also economic) for companies and users.</p> <p>It is important, therefore, that companies understand the importance of supporting IT asset protection specialists with an efficient control system based on AI algorithms that enables IT security management to be strengthened predominantly among operating environments: detection of potentially dangerous anomalous situations; decision support; intelligent agents.</p>
N/A	N/A	How does personality change in the world of influencer marketing?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1882599983	<p>Although these are virtual spaces, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and Instagram are fragments of real reality as well as a stage for more or less positive online experiences for different actors, users. "Social media are virtual spaces but produce real emotions" explains Dr. Brian Primack, director of the University of Pittsburgh's Centre for Research on Media, Technology and Health.</p> <p>While it is true that social media can contribute to the creation of utopian ideals of life and perfect bodies, on the other hand it is increasingly common to find movements that go against the trend, promoted also by celebrities who, for example, speak openly of the use of Photoshop to edit their photos or</p>

						<p>decide to publish photos in which they appear natural. These movements, which often become viral because they are shared by official celebrity accounts, are used to lead young people to adopt ethical behaviours on social media, allowing them to identify with influencers.</p> <p>One of the side effects of being always connected on the internet and on the pages of the influencers is that you can develop a real addiction; therefore, a certain education is desirable for the correct use of social media, marked by the awareness that as much as it can be enviable and perfect, it is still a virtual world that is totally detached from reality</p>
N/A	N/A	Does the use of social media create stress?	Research	Word document	<p>https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2005281911</p>	<p>Each of us has its own specific tolerance for stress, but the one resulting from Social Media overload is a phenomenon that is still little known and should not be underestimated.</p> <p>"There is a very strong concordance between the hours spent on digital technology and the highest levels of Stress and Depression," says The Australian Psychology Society</p> <p>Compared to 5 years ago - when the data of the first Research were reported - today almost 60% of the interviewed adolescents declare to have big problems sleeping and to expose themselves in public after having reviewed the Social Network sites.</p> <p>If on the one hand it is the continuous virtual connection that causes Depression and Anxiety, on the other a person out of two</p>

						<p>claims to use Social Media to calm down and regain balance.</p> <p>This is half of the adolescents interviewed against a proportion of 37% five years ago. It can certainly be said that more than half - almost 60% - of young people become ill because of a continuous connection, but at the same time they are looking for this connection as self-therapy.</p> <p>None of the subjects interviewed resorted to a therapy or asked for help, not even those who were wealthier or those who were more educated and had a peaceful and facilitating family environment. Not even those who have another job at the same time, so they would be inclined to take care of each other. It is, therefore, desirable an education to the correct use of social media, marked by the awareness that as much as it can be enviable and perfect, it is always a virtual world that is totally detached from what is reality.</p>
N/A	N/A	Online security programs: how to block fake news?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1935799284	<p>Every day we are overwhelmed by news that seems to be true, but that in reality are just fake news created on purpose to click or to influence public opinion. After the US elections, the topic of false news has become of primary importance both for political bodies and for hi-tech companies that offer services that are somehow made worse by fake news: think of social networks or engines of research that every day must clash with those who spread news created on purpose to snatch clicks.</p>

						<p>From Facebook to Twitter, via Google and Bing, all the main services we use every day have created tools that allow us to recognize false news and delete them from the News Feed or SERP (Search Engine Result Page). Knowing how to recognize wrong information from real news is not easy, especially for those who have a low level of attitude. The creators of fake news are very adept at following the flow of news and creating hoaxes that may seem true taking inspiration directly from the news stories. Fortunately, there are tools that allow you to recognize false news and defend yourself from the daily attack of fake news creators.</p> <p>Keeping the attention threshold high when surfing the net is not enough to combat a widespread phenomenon of fake news. For this social network, web giants and governments are developing measures to combat fake news. Facebook has turned to users, asking them to promptly report hoaxes and those who produce them. Google, on the other hand, has decided to hit the realities that gain behind it (with the click method) by blocking its banners placed within suspicious blogs. Some countries, like Germany, want to introduce very high fines (up to 50 million). In the meantime, the safest method to counter fake news is to turn to factoring sites, which verify the veracity of published articles in a documented way.</p>
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N/A	N/A	European Union and the Media: what are the interventions for media literacy?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2008499146	<p>By observing the characteristics of a society that has knowledge as its driving force for development, which constantly increases with a collective process, digital literacy can be interpreted as an individual identity that not only allows an individual to live actively in the knowledge society, but also to participate in its development. This participation takes place by exploiting the typical functions available in this company, through an adequate use of available technologies.</p> <p>The Media Literacy represents an essential contribution to the cultural development and progress of a democratic society, and the educational policies of many countries are now beginning to take into account this new need. People with media literacy are able to make their choices with knowledge of the facts, understand the nature of the contents and services and take advantage of the full range of opportunities offered by new communications technologies.</p> <p>They are better able to protect themselves and their families against harmful or offensive content. The development of Media Literacy in all sectors of society should therefore be promoted and its progress carefully monitored (European Commission, 2011).</p> <p>Media literacy is therefore a major challenge for the European Commission, as it contributes to providing European citizens with the tools to better understand the digital environment, which is increasingly prevalent in European society.</p>
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N/A	N/A	Young digital citizens: simple recipients or active participants?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1882606803	<p>Educating towards an active and democratic citizenship should not be reduced to just “civic education”, especially if understood as a mere knowledge of the institutions, their relationships and the mechanisms of civil coexistence, rather it should be configured as a path that educates the values and attitudes of an individual and social ethic together.</p> <p>Communication and information technologies have improved the real possibility of participation of individual citizens. This translates into a concrete opportunity to exercise one's right of citizenship: through participation in consultations; through the evaluation and the influence exercised on the work of the directors; through immediate access to data, documents and information. The consolidation of the digital dimension as a "real space" for the exercise of active citizenship is linked to the familiarity that the individual matures with the use of tools, applications and services that allow the possibility of actively and effectively intervening in local, national and European decision-making processes . This, of course, must be accompanied by a "digital transparency" project implemented by public authorities.</p>
N/A	N/A	How useful is LinkedIn in terms of job search?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030255510	<p>The central idea of the research was to understand how useful it was to subscribe to social networks of professional networks such as LinkedIn.</p>

						<p>Statistics on the number of people who have obtained work through linkedin mediation have been studied.</p> <p>Subsequently, it was noted that the presence of a well-made LinkedIn profile could help in finding a job.</p>
N/A	N/A	Democracy and the risk of hacking: a legitimate fear?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2027438600	<p>The research analysed the risks of cyber-attacks and presents some measures to fight them.</p>
N/A	N/A	Why are there so few women in STEM?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2031734665	<p>The combination of women and science is increasingly under the spotlight: on the one hand, women who approach the world of science must face a large number of prejudices and barriers. On the other hand, girls who look at the university for scientific subjects with curiosity at school often stop themselves out of fear of not succeeding. The general conviction, in both cases, is that women are not led by nature to deal with certain subjects and their degree of difficulty.</p> <p>In the research we wanted to analyse two factors: the first linked to the statistics by countries, discovering the paradox that the relative differences between genders increase in STEM labour in egalitarian spaces like Denmark and Sweden. In comparison, we are not in the depths of the cases in which the less egalitarian countries (women in Romania and</p>

						<p>Lebanon) working in STEM represents a bigger percentage. Conventions and evaluations on the social and family reasons for such discrimination follow</p>
N/A	N/A	Big Data and Internet of things. What are the risks behind?	Research	Word document	<p>https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2031903700</p>	<p>This work explores the world of big data, a phenomenon that is modifying the existing world from an economic and social point of view. Technological progress has extended the Internet to real objects and places, which can now interact with the network and transfer data and information. The connected objects in the world through this new technology are now billions and influence the economy as well as various working environments. However, there are many doubts on the net: "What is the Internet of things?" And "What is the Internet of Things for?"</p> <p>Recent studies on the internet of things have shown that many people do not know what the Internet of Things (IoT) really is, even though they have different devices based on this technology. The IoT approaches the Internet to the real objects of everyday life, objects that are increasingly connected and that are giving life to a dense network in the territory and in all the environments that need control and automation.</p> <p>The conclusions are entrusted to a brief reference to the phenomenon of the internet of things.</p>

N/A	N/A	Influencers Marketing: unlimited growth or 'bubble'?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908969745	<p>- The influencers market has grown steadily in recent years. In the research we mention the particular Instagram sector. More and more people want to become "influencers", but what are the threats? In which world do they act?</p> <p>The trends of the phenomenon will be analysed. It is evident that we are moving towards a professional nature of the discipline of social media.</p> <p>The market does not seem to stop, growth and regulation, urgently needed to regulate the phenomenon with minimum standards.</p> <p>In defence of consumers and in compliance with basic transparency rules.</p>
N/A	N/A	Why people use Tinder and others app dating?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030259281	<p>Tinder is the most used dating and dating app in the western world.</p> <p>At present it has been observed as the virtual spaces have been reaching the great ground in our daily lives, becoming practically essential for daily operation, transforming the way of our relations.</p> <p>The Internet is popularly used for Search for new relationships. Give the impression that this is presented as a real alternative for the search for friendship, of our "half-orange", "soul mate", "Flirt" or just company.</p> <p>The article analyzes the opinions of those who think that this type of apps are detrimental to psychological development and those who attribute a gambling function, underestimating the problem.</p>

						Statistics on users, their social composition and age are shown. In conclusion we can say that the app is used above all as a pastime.
N/A	N/A	How did fake news manipulate information on the migration phenomenon?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2031808626	<p>This article explores the topic of communication - integration through a technical reading of the communicative reality on the phenomenon of international migration and its effects on the global scenario. With particular attention to the Italian picture, where in recent years the distance between reality and perception has widened. This article explores the topic of communication - integration through a technical reading of the communicative reality on the phenomenon of international migration and its effects on the global scenario. With particular attention to the Italian picture, where in recent years the distance between reality and perception has widened.</p> <p>The conclusion is that the diffusion of news, punctually chosen, their amplification and diffusion, contributes to the creation of a common sense against migrants</p>
N/A	N/A	Information overload in the age of Social Media. How it affect the accuracy of the information?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1920661238	Information Overload can lead to "information anxiety," which is the gap between the information we understand and the information that we think that we must understand. The main problems that this trend involves are listed in the research.
N/A	N/A	Gender stereotype in Sport: where are we at?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1920661238	Sport is one of the few areas in modern culture where the body, its image and stereotypes play

					3/buckets/2313524/uploads/2031842711	<p>a predominant role in terms of physical strength, power and aggressiveness. That is why it is in sport itself that gender differences are influenced by the sociocultural context and the socialization process of men and women, where the images of femininity and masculinity are manifested in diversified ways.</p> <p>First of all it seems appropriate to clarify what the meaning of stereotype.</p> <p>Stereotypes are based on beliefs, preconceived ideas and expectations with the behavior of people is evaluated.</p> <p>Gender stereotypes are responsible for the differential treatment to which women and men are subjected, since the beginning of childhood, on the part of those responsible for socialization.</p> <p>Sometimes it is described and reinforced with the idea that it also works as a factor of social control, sustaining stereotypes is keeping the roles of men and women fixed.</p> <p>It analyzes how the sport and its narration are perceived and followed by the female audience.</p> <p>In conclusion we can say that there is still a lot to do, they continue to be typically male and other female sports. Although the situation has improved in recent years (for example, see the success of the women's soccer world cup)</p>
N/A	N/A	What is the role of Facebook affirmation towards ideal self-image and self-esteem?	Research	Word document	N/A	The research showed how Social Media help people to express themselves. Receiving behavioural affirmation by close people

						facilitates the inner movement towards the ideal self.
N/A	N/A	What are the differences between gender equity, gender equality and women's empowerment?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1987817171	Equality is to give the same chances, equity is to give chances to succeed according to their differences, and empowerment is to enable them to succeed. Gender relations determine how equally men and women use, have access to, and control resources.
N/A	N/A	Have Gender Stereotypes Changed Since the Mid-20th Century	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1927311466	Nowadays few women hold positions of power. The interpretation of this research is that the growing education, inclusion and participation of women in the labour market are at the base of an improved perception of their competences and capacities.
N/A	N/A	How to fight bullying on Instagram?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1935479292	Instagram didn't invent bullying. It's a problem that crops up anywhere that people congregate online. Experts say that, as a society, we are failing to teach kids how the Internet works before setting them loose on it, at a time when they're just starting to understand what it means to exert power in relationships. They say that the fight against bullying can't be tackled by tech companies alone: there needs to be buy in from parents, schools and kids themselves.
N/A	N/A	Which is the Social Media are affected by cyberbullying most?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1978930354	Cyberbullying is a phenomenon that dramatically increased in the last 15 years, as it shown from the data of the research carried out on Google. Following up, coursing through this theme, the study shows how the girls have declared being victims of online

						bullying towards text messages, mostly of sexual extortion
N/A	N/A	Are Social Media harmful to your health?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1966070705	The research showed that users who compared themselves to others on the Social Media platform, were more aware of physical ailments, including sleep issues, weight fluctuations and muscle tension. Similar results were found for those experiencing anxiety and depression. The connection between comparisons and symptoms were found more often in people who felt unsure or with lower satisfaction in their lives
N/A	N/A	Who share most fake information on Facebook?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1941813748	The research stated Fake news are a virus that can compromise a whole country. According to mere and recent studies over 65 years old people are the strongest source that share fake information on Facebook. The most important case in this field are the American elections when Donald Trump got a victory against Hilary Clinton in 2016. Fake news altered the final decision of plenty of citizens.
N/A	N/A	How is a fake news born and why they got clicked more than a real news?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1966070705	The research showed that users who compared themselves to others on the Social Media platform, were more aware of physical ailments, including sleep issues, weight fluctuations and muscle tension. Similar results were found for those experiencing anxiety and depression. The connection between comparisons and symptoms were found more often in people who felt unsure or with lower satisfaction in their lives.

N/A	N/A	Who share most fake information on Facebook?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1941813748	The research stated Fake news are a virus that can compromise a whole country. According to mere and recent studies over 65 years old people are the strongest source that share fake information on Facebook. The most important case in this field are the American elections when Donald Trump got a victory against Hilary Clinton in 2016. Fake news altered the final decision of plenty of citizens.
N/A	N/A	How is a fake news born and why they got clicked more than a real news?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1947553193	The words “Fake news” appeared for the first time at the beginning of the 2017 thanks to a Donald Trump tweet. The research showed that, usually, fake news, are based on topic very popular as politics, terrorism, natural disasters, finance and science. If these articles have emotional slit, original story so it comes perceiving as new: it’s the false, mostly on Twitter, beats the true.
N/A	N/A	Are the companies pursuing who has more followers? And which message is important?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908935880	The outcome of this research, independently of the platforms used and the numbers that an influencer has in terms of followers, what matters for the success of an influencer marketing campaign is the relevance of the protagonists with the sponsored product or service as well as their ability to capture the attention of the public.
N/A	N/A	How to make Digital Participation inclusive?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1908938938	In our societies, in information societies, inequalities are significantly structured by exclusions: exclusion from access to technology, exclusion from data, exclusion from knowledge production and circulation,

						<p>and subsequently exclusion from the networks of decision-making. The research showed Continuity is make sure that we're communicating with people on a regular basis. Once the launch has passed, it's important to keep updating people informed about what's going on the platforms and where the ideas are. In conclusion to answer to the initial question we can say that digital inclusion is being made through some activities which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accessible ICT - Assistive technologies - Skills and digital skills - Social Inclusion
N/A	N/A	Here's the digital divide: in which side are you?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/1956557921	<p>The network got, day after day, as the space of the citizenship and the social dimension of the individuals. Starting from its maiden trip, we thought that Internet could be the emancipate tool of the citizens, but The research showed like Internet produce social inequalities as well, that it will be committed by politics to reduce the disparity.</p> <p>Time and space absorb other meaning; being always on, gets a condition that invest contemporary people and affects, always more, new generations.</p>
N/A	N/A	How can online platforms affect a young person's personal development through self-image?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2029763112	<p>Online platforms can both have positive and negative effects on a young person's mind. The issue comes when the person is not well-enough educated on the risks of not knowing the world they got into. Mentally unstable personalities aren't the best candidates to go</p>

						<p>deep in the online community, many things you find there can be discouraging and even offensive in regards of your self-image. The way to be protected from these risks is to know them. This is why media education is very important, especially for young people like teenagers, because those are the core years where you develop your personality and your mental well-being is most at risk.</p>
N/A	N/A	Can an online developed self-image be dangerous for a young person?	Research	Word document	<p>https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2029763129</p>	<p>Online platforms are dangerous for young people if not used properly or well aware of the risks. If a young person is already mentally unstable, joining and taking part in these platforms can cause more harm than good. Even if that young person has no pre-diagnosed mental issues, it is still a risk nevertheless. Parents should be aware of this and raise awareness to their children about what they will encounter while being online. Suicide rates of young people will start dropping when the people affected are informed and taught about the good use of social platforms. They will start to learn to like themselves because of who they are than who they think they should be.</p> <p>Depression of course is inevitable in society and social media isn't the only cause, people will still fall into it because of other reasons like a financial crisis. But that does not mean that we should not all do our best to try and decrease the feeling of low self-esteem in young people that is caused by their perception</p>

						of how they should be or look like presented online.
N/A	N/A	Is the online world increasing or reducing gender discrimination?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2029763024	We can clearly see that the online world is increasing gender discrimination, especially towards women. These new platforms give new spaces for attackers to cause harm, insult, bully, ... Gender inequality was always present and the online world reflects in a sense what is really happening or going through the minds of some people around the globe. It is a pure reflection of the real situation we're living every day. More cyber security should be installed in order to protect women from being harassed, stalked, bullied or anything that can harm them, like we do in the offline world. A tool is a tool and a weapon is a weapon, online gender discrimination should be legitimised and erased to stop other young people (men) from being inspired. All of these can only be done with an increase in security and control on what is posted online and who has access to it.
N/A	N/A	Are women treated on social media differently than men?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2029763095	I think we can all agree that men and women are treated differently online. Women are the main victims of online violence or harassment -mostly caused by other men- just by simply being a woman so turning it into gender violence. Men of course are also victims in a lot of different aspects also, especially if we're speaking about the LGBT+ community, but when it comes to gender violence it generally happens that way round. Women especially

						<p>should be aware and tread carefully on online platforms to avoid any kind of harassment, but would this mean that women can't be themselves nor express what they want to express because of a potential attack? Unfortunately, yes. We cannot currently stop online gender discrimination as there is no way of blocking it through cyber-security methods. The best alternative would be to prepare young women and teach them about this whole world in order to avoid them being affected by these nasty individuals.</p>
N/A	N/A	Who is working and in which ways to improve Internet safety and privacy?	Research	Word document	<p>https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030011830</p>	<p>The Council established a framework which allows the EU to impose targeted restrictive measures to deter and respond to cyber-attacks which constitute an external threat to the EU or its member states More specifically, this decision allows the EU for the first time to sanction persons or entities that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are responsible for cyber-attacks or attempted cyber-attacks. - Provide financial, technical or material support for such attacks. - Are involved in other ways. <p>This framework also applies to cyber-attacks against non-EU states or international organisations where restrictive measures are considered necessary to achieve the objectives of the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP). These cyber-attacks can mean either online harassment, hacking, violent actions, ...</p>

						<p>The Cybersecurity Act voted in the EU Parliament in 2017:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthens the ENISA by granting to the agency a permanent mandate, reinforcing its financial and human resources and overall enhancing its role in supporting EU to achieve a common and high-level cybersecurity. - Establishes the first EU-wide cybersecurity certification framework to ensure a common cybersecurity certification approach in the European internal market and ultimately improve cybersecurity in a broad range of digital products (e.g. Internet of Things) and services.
N/A	N/A	Will we be 100% safe on the internet in the future?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030011858	<p>Technology is always evolving and advancing. Each day we find new methods of online security. Even if an official entity finds new technology that will achieve a total security on the internet, another person would sooner or later find that same technology and use it against them. The internet will never be totally safe, because being purely scientific, different people from different places will come to the same conclusions if they follow the same track. Because of this, there is no way of assuring that someone with the technology to jeopardise online security will not use it.</p>

N/A	N/A	Is it possible for young people to be offline for 1 week? And How about 40-50 year olds?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030112760	It is more and more difficult for young people to stay away from their phones and computers, never mind a whole week. Compared to the older generations, young people grew up with these pieces of technology, they grew up using social media. It became a part of their routine causing an unconscious addiction, like a person that is used to always having a coffee in the morning, if you take that coffee away, the person will not feel the same and will have the necessity to drink that coffee, with social media it's the same. It will not be possible for most young people to not go on the internet for a week if they had a choice. The older generations didn't grow up with these platforms, they got more used to other forms of spending time, so for them, a week without internet would be less "painful" than for a 15 year old.
N/A	N/A	How much time do we spend on average per day on a social platform? What are the differences between the European countries?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030112788	In Europe, around 95% of its population are internet users and 80% of the population are Facebook users. The average time a European spends on social media each day increased 10.7% to 1 hour, 15 minutes (1:15) in 2017, the average time spent declined by 1.9% to 1:14 in 2018. The statistics say that until 2021 the numbers will stay quite stable, meaning that society is learning bit by bit not to use social media as much every day.
N/A	N/A	How effective are fact-checking companies and how	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/363280	After the whole "Fake News" crisis during the past couple of years, bit by bit, people are

		are people processing these companies' recommendations?			3/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030247688	being more aware of what the media is telling them. Fake news spotter companies like the Spanish one called “Newtral”, have become a big source of information for an ever-growing number of followers. The USA has a very large number of fact-checking companies and agencies like “Snopes”, “Fact-Check” or “Politifact” ready to uncover the fake news we find daily online. Most of them have very good rates of “success” and reliability. Nevertheless, people will always fall in the trap of misinformation and we can’t always be sure that these fake news spotting companies are always telling the truth either. Even though some of them can be reliable, the only thing that people can always count on is their own critical analysis of different sources of information.
N/A	N/A	When were the people better informed: in the past or nowadays?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030247706	The quality in the information can be quite subjective. Of course before the internet information was very limited and in non-democratic countries, the information was tapped for the interest of the government, making most of it not reliable. Regardless of the possibility of the information being “fake”, we still have infinite sources of information, where we can find information about everything and anything. People are better informed nowadays, even though some of them fall into the traps of misinformation. We just need to have a better critical way of thinking and be able to process by ourselves

						the information we receive and decide whether to rely on it or not
N/A	N/A	How effective is digital activism? Which are the examples of how digital participation and activism can change something?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030245449	Digital activism has proven to be quite successful in the last decade. Decision makers use the internet as much as we do and if something is shared enough it will captivate their attention and maybe even influence their decisions. We can see how through social media and advocating for climate change, decision makers around the world have taken note, heard young people's concerns and started to make some changes bit by bit, not the point we'd like them to but it's a start. Of course, the world will not be changed through a facebook post and most of them will only raise awareness, but if enough people agree on the same idea and the heads of state see/hear that voice, it increases the chances of making a change. We should not only be active on social media though, changes are also made every day with small actions.
N/A	N/A	What are the best places for digital participation and why?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030245484	Overall, Twitter has proven to be one of the most successful spaces for digital participation for the public. The platform allows you to comment on decision-makers posts where they will receive direct notification of your comment. Another plus is that a lot of these decision makers are quite active on Twitter, and if it's not them it will be their team. Hashtags also allow you to add ideas to a certain topic, making it easier for people to spot and see what you're sharing. You might

						not always be successful, but if you comment, share and debate enough on the platform, the person you're addressing yourself to will see your ideas and hopefully be inspired by them. WYRED on the other hand gives you different opportunities and space. Allowing you to give detailed information and long developments contrary to what Twitter has to offer.
N/A	N/A	Direct or representative democracy. How can digital media change the institutional structure of our societies?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030260778	<p>The dualism between traditional representative democracy and the appearance of so-called direct democracy is certainly one of the common features of modern democracies.</p> <p>This shows how digital has become part of everyday life and in political decision-making processes.</p> <p>The study showed the practical case of Italy and the five-star movement, which by virtue of the consensus has come to the government of the country, and which administers with alternating fortunes some important decisions with the instrument of direct democracy (Rosseau Platform).</p> <p>How to co-opt direct democracy with representative democracy? Interesting data are presented to leave the reader with his own conclusions.</p>
N/A	N/A	What is the right to oblivion and where did it come from?	Research	Word Document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2030257995	Following the recognition of the right to oblivion in the Community ambit, every person must have the right to rectify the personal data concerning him and the "right to cancellation and oblivion", if the storage of

						<p>such data does not comply with the Regulation.</p> <p>In particular, the interested party must have the right to request that their personal data that is no longer necessary for the purposes for which they were collected or otherwise processed, when they have withdrawn their consent or if they are no longer processed are deleted. is opposed to the processing of personal data concerning him or when the processing of his personal data is not otherwise compliant with the Regulation. This right is particularly relevant if the interested party has given consent when he was a minor, and therefore not fully aware of the risks deriving from the treatment, and wants to subsequently eliminate this type of personal data, in particular from the Internet</p>
N/A	N/A	Are Social Medial sources of stress and dependence?	Research	Word document	https://3.basecamp.com/3632803/buckets/2313524/uploads/2027572392	<p>The consequences of excessive use of Social Media range from the feeling of 'invasion' to one's private life to the difficulty of adapting the use of platforms to that of one's friends. They are the so-called forms of 'tecnostress'. Research on the habits of Facebook users shows that these people, once they develop a form of stress, don't give up their smartphone but switch to use the other.</p>

Table 12: Moves' artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
N/A	N/A	<p>How can the Internet get safer for my daily use? What has to be considered, to be safe in the internet? (Part of it: Cyber-Bullying)</p> <p>What can be done against bullying in the Internet and in School?</p>	Research Photograph	Word-Document:	https://wyredproject.eu/2019/06/03/anti-bullying-strategy-of-the-pupils-of-the-centre-for-inclusive-schools/	<p>The (Cyber)bullying project was the final result of the dialogues sessions, a clarification of themes and research questions with the YP. In the last 2 dialogue session before the presentation of the strategy all participants worked on it and proudly presented their strategy to the headmaster. They argue, that the strategy is not only relevant for themselves but also for all their colleagues and the teachers in school.</p>

Table 13: USAL’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
University of Salamanca	Laura Gundín Ovalle, Celia Pino Pérez	Does social networks promote the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-social-networks	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Causes and consequences of disorders resulting from the influence of physical stereotypes present in social networks.</p>
University of Salamanca	Alicia Blázquez Fort, Noelia Brito Díaz, Henar Talavera Delgado	Does social networks promote the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p>

					internet/project/stereotypes-social-networks	<p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Stereotypes and social networks: Social repercussions of influences.</p>
University of Salamanca	Alba Lemus Zahinos, Maribel Ruiz Expósito	Does social networks promote the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-social-networks	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the</p>

						<p>qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Racial stereotypes of young people on social networks.</p>
University of Salamanca	Sofía Gález Planells, María Blanca Navia Antúnez, Silke Villafranca Melcher	Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-education	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Gender gap in Higher Education Studies.</p>
University of Salamanca	Mercedes Martín Gallego, Gema Ramírez Rodríguez, Lucía Rodríguez Aldea	Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research</p>

					stereotypes-education	<p>Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Stereotypes in the educational system: equal opportunities in autonomous communities.</p>
University of Salamanca	Clara Hernández Torres, Annabel Thys	Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-education	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Playing to be equal.</p>

<p>University of Salamanca</p>	<p>Yessica Alonso Domínguez, Raquel Ezcurra Silanes</p>	<p>Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Scientific poster</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-education</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on The harsh reality of gender stereotypes in Spanish compulsory secondary education.</p>
<p>University of Salamanca</p>	<p>Isabel Romero Fondón, Ana Arzo Ibarrola, Guadalupe Galera Murillo</p>	<p>Does teaching-learning processes an impact in the stereotypes?</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Scientific poster</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-education</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet.</p>

						<p>For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Students' perceptions of career choice by gender.</p>
University of Salamanca	María de las Alas Pumarino Rosellón, Emilia del Carmen Vizán Martín	How do young people deal with pressure about self-image?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-and-self-image	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on How beauty stereotypes affect teens.</p>
University of Salamanca	S. Jiménez Pacheco, S. Sánchez Merino	How do young people deal with pressure about self-image?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p>

					and-equality-internet/project/s-tereotypes-and-self-image	<p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on The canon of feminine beauty.</p>
University of Salamanca	N/A	How do young people deal with pressure about self-image?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/s-tereotypes-and-self-image	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the</p>

						<p>qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Physical stereotypes towards overweight people during adolescence.</p>
University of Salamanca	Noelia García Cruz, Elisa León de Santos Martín, Daniel Luis Gómez	How do young people deal with pressure about self-image?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-and-self-image	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researches to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Influence of physical appearance on secondary school students in Salamanca.</p>
University of Salamanca	Carlos Márquez, Mario Manzano	Does Internet influence in sports?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-and-self-image	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct</p>

					tereotypes-sports	<p>fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Sport does not understand gender, sport does not understand distinctions.</p>
University of Salamanca	Sandra Granados Alonso, Lara Martín Sánchez, Ana Yenes Ruano	Does Internet influence in sports?	Research	Scientific poster	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-sports</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p>

						This artefact is focused on Influence of body image in relation to physical activity in 21st century society.
University of Salamanca	N. Zamora, M. Rosón, E. Merchán	Does social media support the gender gap?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-gap-advertising	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Gender gap in advertising campaigns</p>
University of Salamanca	Iliana Veselinova Petkova, Mónica Gil San Isidro	Do stereotypes have an impact in the current society?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/cultural-background-and-stereotypes	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved</p>

						<p>in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on Do you judge the immigrant? The case of Spain.</p>
University of Salamanca	Ángela Castro López, Patricia Gómez Valdivia	Do stereotypes have an impact in the current society?	Research	Scientific poster	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/cultural-background-and-stereotypes</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on the patriarchal fear of the currently empowered woman in Spanish society.</p>

<p>University of Salamanca</p>	<p>Paula Amores González, Noelia Mielgo Talaia, Lidia Plaza Bueno</p>	<p>Do stereotypes have an impact in the current society?</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Scientific poster</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/cultural-background-and-stereotypes</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Indicators of regional stereotypes in the autonomous communities of Spain: Andalusia, Asturias, Galicia and Catalonia.</p>
<p>University of Salamanca</p>	<p>Susana Castilla Herrera, Cinthya Rodondo Mesa</p>	<p>Do stereotypes only related to gender or there are stereotypes related to sexual orientation?</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Scientific poster</p>	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/projects/tereotypes-related-sexual-orientation</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the</p>

						<p>subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Sex stereotypes today</p>
University of Salamanca	S. Martín Hernández, C. Michta Winnicka, M. Rispolis Paco	Do stereotypes only related to gender or there are stereotypes related to sexual orientation?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/stereotypes-related-sexual-orientation	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Stereotypes of sexual orientation in different countries</p>
University of Salamanca	Yolanda Ramos Pastro, Enya	Are there gender stereotypes during childhood?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gend	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative</p>

	María Martínez Díaz				er-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-during-childhood	<p>Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet.</p> <p>This artefact is focused on The value of education in eliminating gender stereotypes from childhood onwards</p>
University of Salamanca	Susana Lahoz Colás, María Rivero Hernández, Laura Sánchez Marcos	Are there gender stereotypes during childhood?	Research	Scientific poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-during-childhood	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca.</p> <p>The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several</p>

						<p>research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Gender stereotypes in children's stories.</p>
University of Salamanca	Azucena Jiménez Heras, Aroa Franco Tejedor, Ingrid Martín Fernández	Are there gender stereotypes during childhood?	Research	Scientific poster	<p>https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/gender-stereotypes-and-equality-internet/project/gender-stereotypes-during-childhood</p>	<p>The social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject “Methodology of Qualitative Research” in the Degree of Pedagogy at the University of Salamanca. The subject is based on Project Based Learning (PBL); each year, students conduct fictitious researches. The professors of the subject are part of the GRIAL Research Group, although they are not directly involved in the WYRED project. They were interested in collaborating with the project and focus the subject in gender stereotypes on the Internet. For this reason, several social dialogues were conducted as part of the subject, several research questions emerged, and the students conducted real researchers to apply the qualitative methodology in topics related to gender and the Internet. This artefact is focused on Gender Roles in Children's Advertising</p>

Table 14: EARLY YEARS: The organisation for young children LBG’s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
EARLY YEARS	C1	Do children really read and understand consent before going online?	<u>PowerPoint Presentation</u>	PPT	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/sites/default/files/project_results/LETS%20SHOW%20THIS%20TO%20THE%20NATION%20consent.pdf	This research project certainly raised the profile of the issue of consent among the researchers, their classmates and teachers and the older children at the school. In response to the research question - Do children really read and understand consent before going online? – the conclusion was a resounding NO! From their research they found out that most children don't read or understand consent before going online and that consent should be for adults and not children. Their conclusions and recommendations proposed that a consent form should (be in simple language; show all peoples opinions; be short or people won't read it; be in paragraphs). consent forms need to be short, to the point, simple language.
EARLY YEARS	C2	Does Cyberbullying happen more often than bullying in real life?			https://platform.wyredproject.eu/sites/default/files/project_results/WYREDCYBER%20BULLYING%20Ppt.pdf	The research concluded that most children have experienced bullying in some form with most agreeing that it is easier to bully online. Also children were confident in reporting a bully. The recommendations made by the children from this research project are as follows: Don't go online as much; Tell someone what happened; Get permission to go online; Don't bully; Have classes on Internet Safety in schools; Don't accept Friend Request from people that you

						don't know; Don't give out personal information online.
EARLY YEARS	C3	Is Hacking illegal?	Performance	Role Play Drama	https://earlyyears-my.sharepoint.com/:v:/g/person/mayor_early-years_org/ESbt0eGtIsJNhbQmXeAiLqsB4xunCSPyMWaQnhVTStQq5Q?e=IcYC4n	Recommendations: Never hack people, You could get arrested for hacking, When you hack other people's account and steal stuff because you don't like them - that makes you a bad person.
EARLY YEARS	C4	Can people tell the difference between real and fake news?	<u>PowerPoint</u> Presentation	PPT	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/sites/default/files/project_results/Our%20wyred%20project%20FAKE%20NEWS.pdf	The children concluded though their research project that: <i>not everything that is in the news is true and sometimes it is very hard to tell the difference between what is real news and what is fake news! our research tells us that people think they can spot fake news most of the time, when in fact they cannot!</i> People should be careful about what they believe- If it seems too good to be true, or silly, it's probably not true! There should be stricter rules for people who make the news and for magazines, newspapers and the internet, so that people are not fooled by fake news reports. If you're not sure if a news report is real or fake, check out other sources to see if you can find out more.
EARLY YEARS	C5	Is self-image more important online than in the real world?	Poster presentation	Poster	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/sites/default/files/project_results/Self%20Image2.jpeg	Recommendations: People should not put up pictures of themselves online; People should not cyberbully or they will get banned; People should not judge themselves based on their self-image.

Table 15: TAU' s artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
TAU Summer Youth University (Hof Hasharon" regional high school, Shfayim,Israel)	S1	How to deal with digital addiction? Are there technological solutions?	Summary Discussions	Word document	www.wyred.com	All students said they are "living in their smartphones" a lot of time every day. Most of them would like to occupy themselves less with their screens. There was a discussion about "screen time": there was a disagreement about the typical time devoted to screens, but most agree that it is hours per day. Some students are busy with their screens four hours a day, maybe even more.
TAU Summer Youth University (Hof Hasharon" regional high school, Shfayim,Israel)	S2	How to deal with fake news? How will this issue look in the future? (likely scenarios)	Summary Discussions	Word document	www.wyred.com	Distinguishing between real and false information on the Internet ("Fake News"): Some participants noted that in many cases the problem is not necessarily false information but information that is only partially true, or biased. Some students think they have the ability to distinguish between true and false info, and some of them say they do not have such ability. Some feel that their ability is only limited to subjects known to them thanks to personal experience. One participant said that in his opinion, this is the only way to distinguish - even though not everyone can personally experience everything. Regarding Scenario 3, one of the students commented (contrary to the views expressed in

						meetings with other groups) that actually adults today have more experience than young people and can better distinguish between false and real information.
TAU Summer Youth University (Hof Hasharon" regional high school, Shfayim,Israel)	S3	How to deal with privacy on the web? How will this issue look in the future? (likely scenarios)	Summary Discussions	Word document	www.wyred.com	Distinguishing between real and false information on the Internet ("Fake News"): Some participants noted that in many cases the problem is not necessarily false information but information that is only partially true, or biased. Some students think they have the ability to distinguish between true and false info, and some of them say they do not have such ability. Some feel that their ability is only limited to subjects known to them thanks to personal experience. One participant said that in his opinion, this is the only way to distinguish - even though not everyone can personally experience everything. The implication is that one should rely on the knowledge and personal experience of others. Some participants noted that the problem also exists in non-digital media and it is not advisable to rely on journalists. They believe that most information in the media (any type of media) is either biased or only partially true.

Table 16: Boundaries observatory C.I.C's artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
Brit School , Croydon Uk	YP1	What are the effects on YP of online LGBT+ discrimination?	Slide deck and video of presentation	PPT/MOV (later MP4)	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/	This group focused on their own extensive experience as LGBTQ+ young people of online discrimination. Their stories focus on the need for resilience in relation to this question, where possible, though their focus is on calling attention to the issue and calling for action.
Brit School , Croydon Uk	YP2	How does online gender discrimination affect mental health?	Slide deck and video of presentation	PPT/MOV (later MP4)	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/	The group chose a creative response to the question, making a video in which one of them wrote the insults they had received online on her body, and then made a film of it, combined with internet research data. The images express their perception of the need for resilience in relation to this question, where possible, though their focus is on calling attention to the issue and calling for action.
Brit School , Croydon Uk	YP3	How do YP manage self-image in online contexts? Are YP approaches to management of self-image online different from older generations?	Slide deck and video of presentation	Videos as part of the research process, videos of presentation and ensuing discussion. A later video with reflections on the process.	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/	This group focused on the differences between their management of self- image as individuals and older generations use. Perhaps the key insight in that respect was the degree of investment, while all use social media and present themselves to some degree, the older generations are less concerned by the difficulties involved. The conclusions focused on the need for resilience and self-respect, which are communicated well in the reflection video they made

Brit School , Croydon Uk	YP4	How do banter and memes affect YP online?	Slide deck and video of presentation	Videos as part of the research process, videos of presentation and ensuing discussion. A later video with reflections on the process.	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/	This group used an auto ethnographic approach, examining their own response to banter and memes and how what can begin as easy joking conversation can swiftly turn toxic. Much of their exploration focused on how this process could be stopped. As with the other groups, the most valuable artefact is arguably the process itself. The growth can best be seen in the confidence and clarity of Lisa in the final reflection video.
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Table 17: PYE's artefacts list

Organisation	Name and surname	Research Question	Artefacts			Comments and Conclusions
			Type	Format	Link	
PYE	C1	Why is fortnight a 12?	Interview dialogue	Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Do you think is violent? No but the concepts are. Do you think messages should be taken out? No because you wouldn't be able to talk to your friends. Do you think people should be able to friend you? Yes but you should have a way to identify them to stay safe. Solo squad or duo do you find people can be rude with their body language? There should be a way you can go into duo and not have to talk to people. (aside: you could just mute it.)
PYE	C2	How to be respectful online?	Verbal&Written	Pamphlet	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-	N/A

					digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	
PYE	C3	Why do people change their appearance to fit in?	Poem& dance	Video&image	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Exploration of body image and how people use social media to change their appearance. Independently came to the conclusion that it's not needed and we are all beautiful in our own way.
PYE	C4	What do year 5's do on the internet	Interview & survey	Video& Text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Through the survey the class discovered what platforms classmates use, how long they spend online and some insights into phone by parents. The interview delved deeper into how two classmates are using the internet, what games they are playing, social media, age appropriateness.
PYE	C5	How do we use tech in the classroom?	Drama Role Play	Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Discussed what tech is used in school and how that impacts learning. Teachers use; YouTube videos to deliver mindfulness exercises, warm up activities, subject specific programs designed for classrooms. Conclusions we have more access to people sharing skills, knowledge or activities that adds to the learning.
PYE	C6	How can we use the internet to express ourselves?	Poster and Animations	Poster & Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Three students invited the class to draw an emoji of how they are feeling right now. Asked if it's easier to draw an emoji or use the premade ones on a phone. Some said drawing gave them more freedom to be exact. Some said having the

					online-and-being-10-years-old	preexisting emojis gave them an image which enabled them to express their emotion and be specific. The group made a poster of the classes emojis. Discovered that there will be 200 new emoji's added to phones. Explored the new animoji feature on the iPhone XR and recorded some insights from classmates. Talked about how animoji let's you see some of the facial expressions which is better than text or voice notes but not as revealing as a video message.
PYE	C7	What do year 5's do online?	Poster	Image	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	Survey as above for emoji group. Poster represents the survey results.
PYE	C8	Do you speak to strangers online?	Speech	Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	How do you stay safe online? You should talk to people and tell them if strangers contact you. What people might do online that could be unsafe. What you could do to stay safe. How to block or report people.
PYE	C9	Why do people change their appearance to fit in?	Short story	Video	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/our-digital-footprints-protecting-ourselves/project/being-online-and-being-10-years-old	As above with other group who explored same question.

PYE	C10	What is digital activism? How can we get involved?				
PYE	C11		Podcasts, pdf	MP3	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/children-rights-digital-society/project/digital-activism-rights-and-getting-involved	<p>Engaged in dialogues around how to use digital tools to raise voices on issues that matter to young people. Informed about the broadcasting industry and the elements that go into a podcast. Develop presenting and public speaking skills. Engage in group work and develop team work skills. Produced 4 podcasts on a variety of youth issues; Social media impact on mental stress around exam time. Raising awareness of bullying and discrimination towards LGBT young people through exploring how LGBT artists & musicians use digital lives to speak out. Creating a ‘sesh’ or ‘nice vibes’ to chill out to in the evenings after study or general life stress. Curating music through digital media to relieve stress and evoke positive feelings. Exploring the link between drill music and youth violence. What is drill and is it inciting more violence amongst young people and why is it going viral? We produced some great content and had some stimulating and engaged dialogue.</p>
PYE	C12	How do we become more educated to get reliable information?	Poetry Pamphlet and live sharing event	Text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/children-rights-digital-society/project/take-back-power-podcast , https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/children-rights-digital-	<p>Young people are paid to participate in the PAR project. They are engaged and committed to the project. Attempted to reconnect after the initial sessions to reengage with further workshops but most of the group had moved on to further education and became unavailable. Working towards forming another group on the theme of youth violence later in the year. Communicating</p>

					society/project/take-back-power	with Lita and Lucy on how we can partner and work together on that. As well as working on this project, this first cohort at the Winchester Project came up with future research questions in regards to their experiences of the Education System, from their perspective as young students of colour, from working class backgrounds. Questions they thought about include: How has nine years of austerity affected their opportunities? Do they feel that schooling helps them live in the world they want to live in? How does Social Media play into their education? Does school feel like a way out, or a cycle keeping them trapped in disadvantage?
PYE	C12	How can we make more positive self images on social media	Podcasts, pdf	MP3	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/self-image-online/project/music-influence-and-social-media	Good engagement from the young people who were present, Interesting dialogue around social media use and impact on mental health, Dialogue around music and social influencers, defining genre and inspiration coming from music. Discussion about how music artists use social media and this influences ‘us’ as listeners. Created a podcasts on ‘our musical aspirations’, ‘positivity’ and ‘defining musical genres – what’s the difference between drill & grime’
PYE	C12	How much are we being followed in our lives and on social media?	Photos of the group sharing their work at the event. Photos of work generated from discussions	Posters and Text	https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/chil-dren-rights-digital-society/project/take-back-power-2	Talk to individuals about social media and digital links to youth violence. All seem engaged and interested to develop further. One girl is particularly interested in talking to MPs and jumping on the platform. 6th December 5-7pm – Introduce myself to the group, talk about WYRED, explore the potential collaboration.

			during the workshops.			Draw out digital links from their discussions and add text to the wall on self-image, gender discrimination, fake news. They invite me to event on the 20th where they are sharing the results of their research. 3rd December 4-5pm – Meet with Lita, learn about what the group have been working on, discuss potential ideas for WYRED and arrange a date and time to come in and meet the group Thursday 13th.
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6. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, 280 participants aged 8-23 from seven countries produced 105 artefacts in Cycle 1 between July 2017- May 2018. There were 33 different types of artefacts.

The activities of Cycle 1 included drama, film, creative digital arts, digitally mediated educational and other informal learning activities and research projects.

Cycle 2 activities covered social, environmental and other research projects. It ran between May 2018 and August 2018 and yielded 52 artefacts across the seven partnering countries. Research topics were bullying, sustainability, politics, digital security, gender, rights, internet safety, cyberbullying, environment, social media, community, life on social media, the environment.

From 8 partners 134 artefacts with the participation of 756 children and young people in Cycle 3 between September 2018 and October 2019. Research topics are influencers on social media, our digital footprints- protecting ourselves, self-image online, gender stereotypes and equality on internet, your lives on social media vs adults, digital participation, gender-stereotypes: the way out and children rights.

During Cycle 1, the participants focused on designing and implementing research activities in order to explore the issues identified in the previous stage, using a range of approaches, with the support of the partner organisations. Each group implemented the activities they designed, using Cycle 2 to adjust their course in the light of the results of the evaluation of the previous cycle activity.

Cycle 1 was a long enough period to work extensively with target groups. Cycle 2 coincided with summer vacations, which is a very difficult period to engage with high school students. Cycle 3 is the most productive period for the creation of the artefacts thanks to the fortnight online events done by project partners. It contributed greatly to increasing and improving project diversity.

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